

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module A: AI, free will and autonomy.

D3.1 MOD. A

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Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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